

Purification of GS loop mutants of ALK2 (ACVR1) to investigate necessary phosphorylation's for SMAD1 activation.

Proteins to be purified:

ACVR1Z-c103

MGHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQ*/SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHACTSGSGSGLPFLVQRTVARQITLLECVGKGRYG
EVWRGSWQGENVAVKIFSSRDEKSWFRETELYNTVMLRHENILGFIASDMTSRHSSTQLWLITHYHEMGSLYDYL
QLTTLDTVSCLRIVLSIASGLAHLHIEIFGTQGKPAIAHRDLKSKNILVKKNGQCCIADLGLAVMHSQSTNQLDVGNN
PRVGTKRYMAPEVLDETIQVDCFDSYKRVDIWAFLVLEVARRMVSNQIVEDYKPPFYDVVPNDPSFEDMRKV
VCVDQQRPNIPNRWFSPTLTLAKLMKECWYQNPSARLTALRIKKTCLKID

ACVR1Z-c104

MGHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQ*/SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHSCASGSGSGLPFLVQRTVARQITLLECVGKGRYG
EVWRGSWQGENVAVKIFSSRDEKSWFRETELYNTVMLRHENILGFIASDMTSRHSSTQLWLITHYHEMGSLYDYL
QLTTLDTVSCLRIVLSIASGLAHLHIEIFGTQGKPAIAHRDLKSKNILVKKNGQCCIADLGLAVMHSQSTNQLDVGNN
PRVGTKRYMAPEVLDETIQVDCFDSYKRVDIWAFLVLEVARRMVSNQIVEDYKPPFYDVVPNDPSFEDMRKV
VCVDQQRPNIPNRWFSPTLTLAKLMKECWYQNPSARLTALRIKKTCLKID

ACVR1Z-c105

MGHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQ*/SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHACASGSGSGLPFLVQRTVARQITLLECVGKGRYG
EVWRGSWQGENVAVKIFSSRDEKSWFRETELYNTVMLRHENILGFIASDMTSRHSSTQLWLITHYHEMGSLYDYL
QLTTLDTVSCLRIVLSIASGLAHLHIEIFGTQGKPAIAHRDLKSKNILVKKNGQCCIADLGLAVMHSQSTNQLDVGNN
PRVGTKRYMAPEVLDETIQVDCFDSYKRVDIWAFLVLEVARRMVSNQIVEDYKPPFYDVVPNDPSFEDMRKV
VCVDQQRPNIPNRWFSPTLTLAKLMKECWYQNPSARLTALRIKKTCLKID

*/ Indicates tev cleavage site.

Expression:

Cells were expressed in Sf9 insect cells using baculo infection system. Cells were transfected and after 96h harvested at 900g before freezing at -20 prior to purification.

Purification:

- Thaw pellets in luke warm water
- Sonicate all other samples for 3 min (5 on, 10 off) on ice for baculo cells.
- Divide each sample into two centrifugation tubes and top up with 'binding buffer' (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5) so each tube is full (aprox 40ml per tube).
- Add 1ml PEI (5%) per tube to precipitate DNA.
- Spin at 21.5k rpm for 50 minutes.

- Incubate lysate with 2.5ml pre-equilibrated Ni-NTA beads at 4C for 1h. (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5)
- Spin down beads at 700g for 10 minutes to separate beads from lysate.
- Pour off lysate.
- Resuspend beads in 50ml binding buffer and load onto gravity flow column (collect flow through)
- Wash with 30ml wash buffer (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 30mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Elute in 7ml elution buffer 1 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 50mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Elute in 3 x 7ml elution buffer 4 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 250mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Run samples on an SDS PAGE gel (mix 5ul of loading dye with 15ul sample, boil for 3 minutes and load 10ul onto the gel.) and run at 160V for 50 minutes.

SDS-PAGE gel of Nickle purification of ACVR1Z-c103, c104 and c105 showing flow through, washes 1 and 2 and four elution fractions. The red box indicates samples taken on for additional purification.

- Pool elution fractions as shown above.
- Add Tev protease to fractions which contain protein
- Concentrate down boxed samples to <5ml and run on a pre-equilibrated GF 75 column for all samples using standard gel filtration buffer (300mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 0.5mM TCEP, pH7.5).
- Collect fractions and run a gel of peak.

SDS-PAGE gel of gel filtration samples (top) and corresponding UV traces from the AKTA runs (bottom) using a GF200 size exclusion column. Speckles on the gel were where microorganisms had grown on the gel prior to photographing them.

ACVR1A-c015 was Ni Rebound to remove lower band contaminants however in the process of doing so enough was lost that there wasn't enough to save.

Mass spec confirmed correct intact mass for all constructs:

Intact mass spec using a QTOF machine indicates all constructs are cleaved, correct to +/- 1Da and contain no initial intrinsic modifications such as phosphorylation.